

Role of Type 2 deiodinase in response to acute lung injury (ALI) in mice

Abbreviated title: Type 2 deiodinase in murine acute lung injury (ALI)

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Thyroid hormone (TH) metabolism, mediated by type 1, 2 and 3 deiodinases (D1, D2, D3) is profoundly affected by acute illness. We examined the role of TH metabolism during ventilator-induced lung injury (VILI) in mice. Mice exposed to VILI recapitulated the serum TH findings of acute illness, namely a decrease in T_3 and TSH and an increase in rT_3 . mRNA expression of D2 showed a 6.4 fold increase and D2 enzymatic activity was increased 2.2 fold. D1 and D3 did not change. Using D2 knock out mice (D2KO) we determined whether the increase in D2 was an adaptive response. Although similar changes in serum TH levels were observed in D2KO and WT mice, D2KO mice exhibited increased susceptibility to VILI compared to wild type mice (WT), as evidenced by poorer alveoli integrity and quantified by lung chemokine and cytokine mRNA induction. These data suggest that an increase in lung D2 is protective against VILI. Similar findings of increased inflammatory markers were found in hypothyroid WT mice exposed to VILI compared to euthyroid mice indicating that the lungs were functionally hypothyroid. Treatment of D2KO mice with T_3 was able to reverse many of the lung chemokine and cytokine profiles seen in response to VILI demonstrating a role for T_3 in the treatment of lung injury. We conclude that TH metabolism in the lung is linked to the response to inflammatory injury and speculate that D2 exerts its protective effect by making more TH available to the injured lung tissue.

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Thyroid hormone (TH, here denoting the active hormone 3,5,3'-triiodothyronine (T_3) and its precursor thyroxine (T_4)) is necessary for the normal development and function of virtually every vertebrate tissue. While the thyroid gland is predominantly responsible for the production and release of T_4 , the cellular bioavailability of the active T_3 depends on TH specific transporters and tissue TH metabolism. Metabolism of TH is regulated by three iodothyronine deiodinases. Both type 1 (D1) and type 2 (D2) deiodinases serve to generate bioactive T_3 by outer ring deiodination of T_4 . While D1 contributes to plasma T_3 levels, D2 has a major role in the intracellular generation of the active TH in mouse. In contrast, type 3 iodothyronine deiodinase (D3) inactivates TH by inner-ring deiodination of T_4 to reverse T_3 (r T_3 ; 3',5,3-triiodothyronine) and T_3 to 3,3'-diiodothyronine (T_2), both biologically inactive compounds (1).

While studies have elucidated the dynamic effects of TH action on brain, bone, liver (2-5) and maturation of the fetal lung (6, 7), little is known regarding the role of TH in adult lung physiology. Up until now, evidence to suggest that TH influences adult lung physiology is indirect and based on the presence of thyroid hormone receptors (8), deiodinases (9-12) and measured TH concentrations (10, 13, 14) in the lung.

In severe illness associated with lung injury there are systemic changes in circulating TH levels similar to those observed in other illnesses, known as "non-thyroidal illness" (NTI). They are characterized by a decrease in serum T_4 , T_3 and TSH with an increase in r T_3 (15, 16). The mechanisms behind changes in serum TH concentrations that occur in NTI include induction of central hypothyroidism due to a diminution in hypothalamic TRH (Thyrotrophin-releasing hormone). This can be

signaled by a localized increase in hypothalamic T_3 catalyzed by altered expression of hypothalamic iodothyronine deiodinases D2 and D3 (17).

It is generally accepted that extra-thyroidal conversion of T_4 to T_3 is decreased in illness due to a reduction in both hepatic/renal D1 activity and skeletal muscle D2 activity. In addition to these changes, there may be a reactivation of hepatic and skeletal muscle D3, which leads to increased production of rT_3 (18, 19). However, data from D1, D2 and D3 knockout mice suggest that these enzymes may have little contribution to the low serum T_3 found in acute illness (9, 20). Since circulating T_3 decreases before many T_3 -dependent tissues become T_3 deficient, it is controversial whether tissues during severe illness are functionally hypothyroid as reflected by the low serum or tissue levels of TH (20, 21). The purpose of the current study was to determine whether deiodinase activity as a marker of TH metabolism in the lung was altered in response to lung injury and whether the changes associated with NTI were adaptive or maladaptive. We examined the role of TH metabolism in a mouse model of ventilator-induced lung injury (VILI) (22-25). We demonstrate that TH concentrations in blood recapitulate NTI after VILI. Furthermore using mice deficient in deiodinases we were able to demonstrate that D2 is protective to the effects of VILI. Furthermore, hypothyroid mice had more severe acute inflammatory lung injury than euthyroid mice in response to VILI. We conclude that TH metabolism in the lung may be linked to the response to inflammatory injury and speculate that D2 exerts its protective effect by making more TH available to the injured lung tissue.

Results

Serum thyroid function tests in WT mice after exposure to VILI

After 4h of VILI, T_3 serum levels were reduced by $16.1\% \pm 4.5$ compared to SB animals (67.1 ± 3.6 vs 80.0 ± 2.3 ng/dl, $p < 0.01$) (Fig. 1). Similarly, the circulating

TSH levels were significantly reduced to undetectable levels compared to WT animals control (<10 vs 44.5 ± 14.3 mU/L, $p < 0.05$) (Fig. 1). Although no significant differences were found in the serum levels of T_4 between ventilated and SB animals (2.4 ± 0.2 vs 2.6 ± 0.2 $\mu\text{g/dl}$) (Fig. 1), a significantly increase in rT_3 was observed after mechanical ventilation (18.9 ± 2.7 vs 29.3 ± 2.1 ng/dl of VILI, $p < 0.05$) (Fig. 1). The decreased T_3 and TSH and the increased rT_3 serum levels observed in this model of acute inflammatory lung injury is in agreement with the clinical settings of critical illness seen in patients with acute lung injury (ALI) or animal models of acute illness (26-33).

Effect of VILI on D1, D2 and D3 expression in lung

Although we detected D1, D2 and D3 mRNA in the lungs of SB animals, in agreement with previous reports (11, 12), expression of D1 was lower than D2 (Ct for D1, 31.3 ± 0.2 ; Ct for D2, 28.3 ± 0.4). No differences in D1 and D3 mRNA levels were observed between VILI and SB WT animals (Fig. 2A). Curiously, D2 mRNA expression was increased 6.4 ± 1.8 fold change ($p < 0.01$) over SB WT mice after VILI (Fig. 2A). Retrospective review of our prior expression profiling results in murine models of VILI indicated that D2 mRNA was induced in VILI-challenged WT mice (9.5 fold change at 30 ml/kg tidal volume and 26.2 fold change at 40 ml/kg tidal volume)(34, 35).

Immunohistochemistry of the SB WT lungs revealed D2 present in airway epithelium and in the pulmonary endothelium (Fig. 2B, inflammatory cells were not present in control lungs). VILI-challenged WT mice demonstrated markedly increased D2 protein in pulmonary endothelium and epithelium compared with SB WT mice (Fig. 2B) in agreement with the increased D2 mRNA expression. D2

immunoreactivity was not detected in the inflammatory cells (indicated by asterisk in Fig. 2B). Specificity of the anti D2 antibody was demonstrated by negligible staining of lungs of D2KO mice and lungs of WT mice stained with the preimmune serum (Fig. 2B, lower panels). In agreement with the strong induction of D2 mRNA and protein levels after mechanical ventilation, D2 enzymatic activity was 2.2 ± 0.6 -fold higher ($p < 0.05$) compared to SB WT animals (Fig. 2C).

D2KO mice have increased susceptibility to inflammatory lung injury

To define whether the D2 induction by mechanical ventilation in WT mice had a protective or detrimental role in inflammatory lung injury, we exposed mice with targeted D2 deletion to VILI. Both VILI-challenged WT and D2KO mice exhibited an increase in lung vascular permeability compared to SB animals as shown by the increase of protein content in BAL (1.9 ± 0.3 fold change for WT, $p < 0.05$ and 2.9 ± 0.4 fold change for D2KO, $p < 0.01$) (Fig. 3A). D2KO mice had a greater increase in BAL protein content following VILI compared to WT mice, though this difference did not reach significance ($p = 0.058$) (Fig. 3A). There were no differences in inflammatory content as determined by histopathologic analysis in SB WT and D2KO mice (Fig. 3B). In contrast, after exposure to VILI, both groups of animals showed increased inflammatory cell infiltration in the alveolar wall and hyaline membrane formation. However, in relation to WT animals, D2KO mice exposed to VILI demonstrated greater polymorphonuclear leukocyte infiltration and hyaline membrane formation indicated by green and red arrows respectively (Fig. 3B). D2KO mice following VILI-exposure displayed markedly elevations in lung chemokine and cytokine levels over SB as compared to WT animals: Interleukin-6 (IL-6) (3.1 ± 1.1 fold, D2KO vs WT, $p < 0.05$); interleukin-1 β (IL-1 β) (1.8 ± 0.2 fold, $p < 0.001$);

Chemokine (C-X-C motif) ligand 1 (Cxcl-1) (2.6 ± 0.9 fold, $p < 0.05$), Tnf- α (2.4 ± 0.7 fold, $p < 0.05$) and Chemokine (C-X-C motif) ligand 2 (Cxcl-2) (4.4 ± 0.6 fold, $p < 0.001$) (Fig. 3C).

On the basis of chemokine and cytokine induction and histological analysis of VILI-mediated alterations in lung morphology, D2KO mice appear more susceptible to VILI compared to WT mice, suggesting that the presence of D2 is protective against VILI. As an unbiased approach to elucidate additional transcriptional pathways that underlie the D2KO lung phenotype, we used microarray analysis of lungs from WT and D2KO, both SB and after VILI. This approach led to the identification of additional genes with reported roles in regulation of inflammation and damage, including Hsp1 (Heat shock protein 1), Serpine 3G, Mmp9 (Matrix metalloproteinase 9) and Retnlg (Resistin-like gamma) (Fig. 3D).

Expression of Hsp1 is well described in lung and in response to a variety of stressors. In vitro data, as well as data from various animal models of acute lung injury, demonstrate that Hsp1 has an important cytoprotective role during lung inflammation and injury(36, 37). We found much lower expression of Hsp1 in D2KO than WT mice after VILI-challenged (Fig. 3D), implicating the possibility of further decreased cytoprotection during lung inflammation in D2KO mice. Also, in WT animals, exposure to VILI induced Serpine 3G (Fig. 3D), a serine protease inhibitor that is down regulated by a hypoxia inducible factor (Hif) mechanism (38). However Serpine 3G was downregulated after VILI in D2KO mice. Most dramatically, Mmp9 was significantly less induced (55% of WT animals) in VILI exposed D2KO mice (Fig. 3D). Mmp9 is a gelatinase that has a protective role during inflammatory lung injury(39, 40). Finally, Retnlg is a member of a family of cysteine-rich secreted proteins, referred to as 'resistin-like molecules' or 'found in inflammatory zone' that

increase in expression during inflammation and cytokine immune responses(41), although its function is still not clear. After VILI, the induction of *Retnlg* was completely absent in D2KO whereas a 3.5-fold induction was observed in WT animals (Fig. 3D). In summary, these data indicate that the absence of D2 modifies the lung transcriptome after VILI challenge, increasing the inflammatory response and decreasing cytoprotective defenses against VILI.

Treatment of D2KO with L-T3 decreases susceptibility to inflammatory lung injury

We determined whether a potential lung local hypothyroidism accounts for the increased susceptibility of D2KO to inflammatory lung injury by pre-treating these mice with 0.2 μ g/100 gm L-T3 before challenge them to VILI (Fig. 4). In general, the protective markers of inflammation, eg. *Serpine 3g* in D2KO untreated mice were 0.5 fold change relative to SB compared to 1.1 fold in D2KO treated with L-T3. More dramatic was the -8.3 reduction seen in *Hsp1* expression after VILI that stimulated 2.8 fold in the LT-3 treated D2KO mice after treatment with L-T3. *MMP9* and *Rslg* did not have a significant change with treatment. In addition, L-T3 treatment significantly reduced the proinflammatory markers (*Cxcl1*, *TNF*, *IL1b* and *Cxcl2*) in D2KO mice (except for *IL6*).

Serum thyroid function, D1 and D3 mRNA expression in D2KO mice exposed to VILI

At baseline D2KO mice differed from the WT mice only in a markedly elevated TSH with similar serum T_4 , T_3 and rT_3 concentrations(42, 43). After exposure to VILI D2KO mice had a significant decrease in T_3 and TSH concentrations (82.3 ± 1.5 vs.

76.1 ± 2.5 ng/dl and 262.3 ± 56.2 vs. 63.4 ± 17.0 mU/L, respectively) and a significant increase in serum rT3 levels (22.1 ± 2.8 vs. 31.7 ± 1.5 ng/dl) compared to SB animals (Fig. 5A). No significant changes were observed in serum T₄ concentrations (2.5 ± 0.2 vs. 2.3 ± 0.1 µg/dl) (Fig. 5A). Serum TSH concentration remained significantly higher in D2KO compared to WT animals when both received VILI (Fig. 4A).

Lung D1 and D3 mRNA expression in SB D2KO mice and those exposed to VILI were analyzed by qPCR. In SB mice, D1 mRNA was 1.9 ± 0.2 fold higher in lung tissue of D2KO compared to WT mice (p < 0.05) (Fig. 5B). After D2KO mice were exposed to VILI, the levels of D1 were reduced by 0.4 ± 0.1 fold similar in absolute value to the WT mice after 4h of mechanical ventilation (Fig. 5B). Although an increase of D3 levels was detected in D2KO mice after VILI as compared to SB animals, the difference did not reach significance. However, a significant increase in D3 mRNA was observed after VILI in the D2KO compared to the WT mice (2.4 ± 0.5 fold) (Fig. 5B).

Response of D1KO mice to VILI

To further understand the role of D1 in inflammatory lung injury, D1KO mice were exposed to VILI. As shown in Figs. 6A and 6B, both WT and D1KO mice had the same degree of inflammatory inflation after VILI as observed by BAL protein content and by histological examination, respectively. There were no differences in the expression of lung chemokines and cytokines (IL-6, IL-1β, Cxcl1 and Tnf-α) levels between WT and D1KO mice exposed to VILI with exception of Cxcl2 that was increased by 197% in D1KO relative to WT animals exposed to VILI (Fig. 6C). In addition, no significant differences in Hsp1, Serpine 3G, Mmp9, and Retnlg were observed between D1KO and WT animals exposed to VILI (Fig. 6D). These results

indicated that the absence of D2, but not D1, increase the susceptibility to VILI. The observation that D1 play less role in response to lung injury than D2 is in agreement with the low expression of D1 mRNA and undetectable D1 enzymatic activity in the lungs of WT mice.

Hypothyroidism and susceptibility to VILI

D2KO mice are more susceptible to VILI than WT mice, however we did not detect differences in serum TH concentrations between WT and D2KO mice. To investigate whether TH deprivation in the lung after VILI reproduced the findings in the D2KO, globally hypothyroid mice were given to VILI. Induction of hypothyroidism was confirmed by serum T₃, T₄ and rT₃ at low level or below the detection. TSH levels in SB and mice with VILI were markedly elevated (15848 ± 3020 vs 24481 ± 1594 mU/L , p<0.05, respectively) .

Hypothyroid SB mice lung had increased BAL protein content compared to euthyroid SB mice (Fig. 7). Similar trends were found in hypothyroid VILI mice but it did not reach significance (0.4 ± 0.03 vs 0.31 ± 0.01 mg/mL) (Fig 7). Hypothyroid VILI treated WT mice had marked elevations in lung chemokines and cytokine levels as compared to euthyroid animals (Fig 7): IL-6 (676.9 ± 67.8 vs 417.5 ± 108.52, p<0.05); IL-1β (1215.51 ± 218.8 vs 423.7 ± 53.7, p<0.01); Cxcl1 (365.6 ± 27.7 vs 149.5 ± 25.2, p<0.05); TNF-α (501.8± 81.2 vs 244.1 ± 25.1, p<0.05); Cxcl2 (6370 ± 1267 vs 254.1 ± 60.3, p<0.001). On the basis of chemokine and cytokine induction, hypothyroid mice had increased susceptibility to VILI.

Hypothyroidism did not modify the expression of D2 mRNA in the lungs of SB WT mice (Fig. 7) but, as expected, we observed a significant increase in D2 enzymatic activity (Fig. 7). Curiously, in contrast to the results observed in euthyroid

animals, exposure to VILI neither induced D2 mRNA nor enzymatic activity in hypothyroid animals.

Discussion

Our results show that VILI produced upregulation of lung D2 mRNA, protein and enzymatic activity. Furthermore we demonstrate that D2 upregulation is likely protective as D2KO mice (which lack D2) have more severe lung injury. One interpretation is that in VILI, induction of D2 may be adaptive to the circulating low T_3 levels in order to generate more local T_3 . Alternatively, D2 could be up-regulated in response to the local injury as part of an inflammatory pathway involving nuclear factor- κ B (NF- κ B) (Fig 7). NF- κ B, an important mediator of immune and inflammatory responses, has been strongly implicated in acute lung injury(44-49). Evidence supports that NF- κ B induces transcription of human and rat D2 gene expression and indeed, a potent NF- κ B binding site has been demonstrated in the human D2 gene(50, 51).

Interestingly in humans with sepsis and sepsis-associated ALI, D2 is associated with susceptibility to ALI (52). European Americans carrying the G allele of D2 coding SNP (rs225014, Thr92Ala) were protected against sepsis-associated ALI. Studies addressing functional consequences of the Thr92Ala SNP are still unclear(53). Discrepant results can be explained by the complex process of D2 regulation, which involves both transcriptional and post-transcriptional mechanisms. As D2 variants conferred ALI susceptibility in human and D2 expression is increased in VILI and appears to dampen VILI-mediated inflammatory responses in mouse, together these results strengthen the hypothesis that TH metabolism is intimately linked to the response to inflammatory lung injury.

The induction of D2 by mechanical ventilation in WT mice may constitute a protective mechanism against VILI by compensating for the local reduction of TH signaling as shown in critical illness(54, 55). In D2KO mice exposed to VILI, the downregulation of D1 would decrease T₃ production whereas the increase in D3 would inactivate TH, plus its natural absence of D2, the total outcome would be the failure to maintain active T₃ locally and possibly a relatively hypothyroid status of the lung of D2KO compared to WT mice. All of the above suggest that severe lung damage might be associated with hypothyroidism in lung. Hypothyroidism can aggravate lung injury by impedance of alveolar fluid clearance resulting in persistent hypoxia; enhanced cell damage, reduced cell proliferation, altered alveolar macrophage populations, and depressed antioxidant defense systems(56). In fact, decreased serum TH levels have been associated with worsening pulmonary function in lung injury or during sepsis (57) and consistent with these observations, administration of TH to patients with respiratory distress syndrome and sepsis improves lung compliance(58). In agreement with these studies, we demonstrated that hypothyroidism worsen the lung damage after VILI. Although we did not directly measure the TH content of the lung tissue during VILI due to difficulties in measurement and interpretation of intracellular TH levels, evidence presented here demonstrates that the profile of inflammatory gene expression in VILI of D2KO lung is similar to hypothyroid lung. Consistently, treatment of D2KO mice with L-T₃ was able to reverse the profiles of expression of the proinflammatory markers by reducing them and increasing the protective markers. Together, our data suggests that the lungs of D2KO mice are relatively hypothyroid during the induction of acute lung injury and that T₃ treatment is protective against inflammatory lung injury.

In summary, the induction of D2 expression (RNA and protein) and activity after mechanical ventilation constitutes a protective mechanism against VILI, likely by compensating for the local reduction of TH signaling which may serve to dampen the inflammatory response to VILI. This work supports a role for D2 in the regulation of response to acute lung injury (Fig 8).

Methods

Experimental animals

All experiments were approved by the Animal Care and Use Committee of the University of Chicago. Type 2 deiodinase deficient (D2KO) and Type 1 deiodinase knock out (D1KO) male mice were generated and propagated as described (43, 59). Mice were 80-100 days of age at the time of analyses and were housed under standard conditions with free access to food and water.

Induction of Hypothyroidism and Treatment with L-T3

TH deprivation was induced in 12-15 male WT mice by feeding with a low-iodine (LoI) diet for 15 days (Harlan Teklad, Madison, WI). On day 15th, animals receive an IP injection of 10mU of bovine TSH and, two hours later an injection of I¹³¹ (150 mCi, in 0.2 ml of saline). 4 weeks after injection, ventilator induced lung injury was applied on hypothyroid mice.

In a separate group of experiments D2KO mice were treated with 2 µg/100 gm L-T3 q day for 5 days. Two hours after the last injection, the mice were randomly allocated to the VILI group (6 mice) or spontaneously breathing (SB) controls (6 mice).

Model of Ventilator Induced Lung Injury

Groups of mice (WT animals, n=8/group, D2KO, n=6/group, D1KO, n=6/group, hypothyroid WT mice, n=6/group) were randomly allocated to either the SB or VILI as

we have previously described (34, 35). Mechanical ventilation experiments were performed in age-matched males after anesthesia with inhaled isoflurane followed by intraperitoneal ketamine/xylazine. Mice were intubated (20-gauge catheter) and placed on mechanical ventilation (Harvard Apparatus, Holliston, MA, USA) at room air, tidal volume of 40 ml/kg 65 breaths/min, and positive end expiratory pressure of 0 cm H₂O for 4 hours as previously described (34). Ventilated animals were monitored with intermittent blood pressure and arterial blood gas monitoring to ensure adequate perfusion and received 8 ml/kg 0.9% saline at the initiation of ventilation and at 2h after the onset of ventilation. Deep anesthesia was maintained with ketamine/xylazine throughout the experiment. Control mice were allowed to breathe spontaneously for 4 hours under same anesthesia and intubating treatment.

Bronchoalveolar lavage (BAL)

BAL was recovered as we previously described (60) for determination of proteins level. Briefly, mice underwent bronchoalveolar lavage (BAL) of both lungs with Hank's balanced salt solution (1mL/mouse). Lavage samples were centrifuged at 500 X *g* on a refrigerated microcentrifuge for 20 min. The supernatant was aliquot for protein assays using the Bio-Rad DC Protein Assay (Bio-Rad Laboratories, Hercules, CA).

Histology and Immunohistochemistry

To characterize VILI-mediated alterations in lung morphology, left lungs (3 animals / group) were excised from the mainstem bronchus at death and placed immediately in formalin overnight, followed by embedding in paraffin for histological evaluation by

hematoxylin and eosin staining as we previously described (60). For analysis of D2 protein localization, the lung samples were deparaffinized and rehydrated by passage through graded alcohols to water, and placed in a pressure cooker with citrate buffer, pH 6.0, for 1 minute after reaching boiling temperature to retrieve antigenic sites masked by formalin fixation. The tissue sections were then placed in 0.5% v/v hydrogen peroxide /methanol for 10 minutes, to inactivate endogenous peroxidase activity: blocked for 20 minutes with normal horse serum (Vectastain Elite ABC Kit; Vector Laboratories, Burlingame, CA), and subsequently incubated for 1h at room temperature with the primary rabbit anti-D2 antibody (generously provided by Antonio C. Bianco, Harvard Medical School, Boston, Massachusetts) (working dilution: 1/100) or with the preimmune serum as a negative control stain. The primary antibody was detected using the ImmPress polymerized reporter enzyme staining system (ImmPRESS reagent kit, Vector Laboratories, Burlingame), according to the manufacturer's specifications. The immunostaining was visualized with the Vector novaRed substrate kit for peroxidase (Vector Laboratories, Burlingame), following the specifications of the manufacturer. Counterstaining was performed with hematoxylin (Vector hematoxilin QS nuclear counterstain, Vector Laboratories, Burlingame). Each sample was graded ($n=3$ /group) from 0 to 3+ in different locations covering the pulmonary epithelium (including airway epithelium and type II pneumocytes), the pulmonary endothelium, and inflammatory cells infiltrate.

Measurement of specific mRNA content in lung by quantitative PCR (qPCR)

Total RNA was isolated from whole lungs of VILI-challenged and SB mice (6-8 per group) for expression profiling as previously described (34). Transcript levels of Serpine 3G, Matrix metalloproteinase 9 (MMP9), Heat shock protein 1 (Hsp1),

Resistin-like gamma (Remlg), the mouse chemokines and cytokines [interleukin (IL)-1 β , IL-6, Chemokine (C-X-C motif) ligand 2 (Cxcl2), Chemokine (C-X-C motif) ligand 1 (Cxcl1) and Tumor necrosis factor alpha (Tnf- α)] as well as for the deiodinases D1, D2 and D3 were measured by qPCR in 96-well microtiter plates with an ABI Prism 7700 Sequence Detector System (Applied Biosystems, Foster City, CA, USA). Amplification of the housekeeping gene RNA polymerase II (Rp2) was used as internal control. The oligonucleotide primers were designed to cross introns (Supplementary table S1). Experimental protocols were based on the manufacturer's recommendation using the *TaqMan* Gold RT-PCR Core Reagents Kit (Applied Biosystems). Experimental parameters were 48°C for 30 min followed by 40 cycles of 95°C for 15 s and 60°C for 1 min. A relative quantitative method was used to analyze changes in gene expression in a given sample relative to an untreated control sample, and specific mRNA transcript levels were expressed as fold difference with exception of the hypothyroid mice, where are shown the values relative to WT euthyroid mice as 100.

Measurements of THs and TSH concentrations in serum

Blood was collected for measurement of serum thyroid hormone and TSH concentration levels at baseline, after induction of hypothyroidism and after 4 hours of VILI exposure or mice breeding spontaneously. Serum TSH was measured in 50 μ l of serum using a sensitive, heterologous, disequilibrium double antibody precipitation RIA, and results were expressed in bioassayable TSH units (61). Serum T₄ and T₃ concentrations were measured by antibody coated tube RIAs (Siemens Medical Solutions Diagnostics, Los Angeles, CA) using 25 and 50 μ L of serum, respectively. rT₃ was measured in 35 μ L of serum by RIA using reagents from Adaltis Italia (Rino, Italy). All samples were individually analyzed for each mouse. Due to the

previously reported suppression of THs with ketamine/xylazine (62), comparisons were made between the ventilated and SB animals, where both groups were treated with the anesthetic.

D2 enzymatic activity

D2 enzymatic activity was performed as described (63) with the following modifications: 100 µg protein of tissue homogenates in 100 µl reaction mixture containing 0.1 M phosphate buffer (pH 7), 1 mM EDTA, 20 mM dithiothreitol, 1 mM propylthiouracil, 100,000 cpm [¹²⁵I] T₄, and 2 nM unlabeled T₄ were incubated at 37 C for 1 h. Saturating levels of unlabeled T₃ (1 µM) were added to the reaction mixture to inhibit the D3 enzyme.

Statistical analysis

Values are reported as mean ± SE with the exception of the quantitative RT-PCR (qPCR) cytokine and chemokine expression data of D1KO and D2KO mice that are presented as mean fold change ± SE. Statistical analysis was performed with Student's *t* test.

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References:

1. Bianco AC, Salvatore D, Gereben B, Berry MJ, & Larsen PR (2002) Biochemistry, cellular and molecular biology, and physiological roles of the iodothyronine selenodeiodinases. *Endocr Rev* 23(1):38-89.
2. Alkemade A (2009) Central and peripheral effects of thyroid hormone signalling in the control of energy metabolism. *J Neuroendocrinol* 22(1):56-63.
3. Williams GR (2008) Neurodevelopmental and neurophysiological actions of thyroid hormone. *J Neuroendocrinol* 20(6):784-794.
4. Gogakos AI, Duncan Bassett JH, & Williams GR (2010) Thyroid and bone. *Arch Biochem Biophys* 503(1):129-136.
5. Ness GC (1991) Thyroid hormone. Basis for its hypocholesterolemic effect. *J Fla Med Assoc* 78(6):383-385.
6. Ansari MA, de Mello DE, & Devaskar UP (2000) Effect of prenatal glucocorticoid on fetal lung ultrastructural maturation in hyt/hyt mice with primary hypothyroidism. *Biol Neonate* 77(1):29-36.
7. Bizzarro MJ & Gross I (2004) Effects of hormones on fetal lung development. *Obstet Gynecol Clin North Am* 31(4):949-961, xii.
8. Keijzer R, *et al.* (2007) Expression of thyroid hormone receptors A and B in developing rat tissues; evidence for extensive posttranscriptional regulation. *J Mol Endocrinol* 38(5):523-535.
9. Boelen A, *et al.* (2008) Type 3 deiodinase is highly expressed in infiltrating neutrophilic granulocytes in response to acute bacterial infection. *Thyroid* 18(10):1095-1103.
10. Escobar-Morreale HF, Obregon MJ, Hernandez A, Escobar del Rey F, & Morreale de Escobar G (1997) Regulation of iodothyronine deiodinase activity as studied in thyroidectomized rats infused with thyroxine or triiodothyronine. *Endocrinology* 138(6):2559-2568.
11. Ohba K, Yoshioka T, & Muraki T (2001) Identification of two novel splicing variants of human type II iodothyronine deiodinase mRNA. *Mol Cell Endocrinol* 172(1-2):169-175.
12. Wagner MS, *et al.* (2003) Hypothyroidism induces type 2 iodothyronine deiodinase expression in mouse heart and testis. *J Mol Endocrinol* 31(3):541-550.

13. Escobar-Morreale HF, Obregon MJ, Escobar del Rey F, & Morreale de Escobar G (1995) Replacement therapy for hypothyroidism with thyroxine alone does not ensure euthyroidism in all tissues, as studied in thyroidectomized rats. *J Clin Invest* 96(6):2828-2838.
14. Pedraza PE, Obregon MJ, Escobar-Morreale HF, del Rey FE, & de Escobar GM (2006) Mechanisms of adaptation to iodine deficiency in rats: thyroid status is tissue specific. Its relevance for man. *Endocrinology* 147(5):2098-2108.
15. Sen S, Dulchavsky SA, & Dutta S (1993) Effects of triiodothyronine (T3) supplementation upon ozone-induced lung injury. *Free Radic Res Commun* 18(5):299-308.
16. Ture M, Memis D, Kurt I, & Pamukcu Z (2005) Predictive value of thyroid hormones on the first day in adult respiratory distress syndrome patients admitted to ICU: comparison with SOFA and APACHE II scores. *Ann Saudi Med* 25(6):466-472.
17. Warner MH & Beckett GJ (Mechanisms behind the non-thyroidal illness syndrome: an update. *J Endocrinol* 205(1):1-13.
18. Chopra IJ (1997) Clinical review 86: Euthyroid sick syndrome: is it a misnomer? *J Clin Endocrinol Metab* 82(2):329-334.
19. Peeters RP, et al. (2005) Increased thyroxine sulfate levels in critically ill patients as a result of a decreased hepatic type I deiodinase activity. *J Clin Endocrinol Metab* 90(12):6460-6465.
20. Peeters RP, et al. (2005) Tissue thyroid hormone levels in critical illness. *J Clin Endocrinol Metab* 90(12):6498-6507.
21. Arem R, et al. (1993) Reduced tissue thyroid hormone levels in fatal illness. *Metabolism* 42(9):1102-1108.
22. Dreyfuss D, Soler P, Basset G, & Saumon G (1988) High inflation pressure pulmonary edema. Respective effects of high airway pressure, high tidal volume, and positive end-expiratory pressure. *Am Rev Respir Dis* 137(5):1159-1164.
23. Ranieri VM, et al. (1999) Effect of mechanical ventilation on inflammatory mediators in patients with acute respiratory distress syndrome: a randomized controlled trial. *JAMA* 282(1):54-61.
24. Tremblay L, Valenza F, Ribeiro SP, Li J, & Slutsky AS (1997) Injurious ventilatory strategies increase cytokines and c-fos m-RNA expression in an isolated rat lung model. *J Clin Invest* 99(5):944-952.
25. Tremblay LN, Miatto D, Hamid Q, Govindarajan A, & Slutsky AS (2002) Injurious ventilation induces widespread pulmonary epithelial expression of

- tumor necrosis factor-alpha and interleukin-6 messenger RNA. *Crit Care Med* 30(8):1693-1700.
26. Boelen A, *et al.* (2004) Contribution of interleukin-12 to the pathogenesis of non-thyroidal illness. *Horm Metab Res* 36(2):101-106.
 27. Boelen A, *et al.* (2004) Simultaneous changes in central and peripheral components of the hypothalamus-pituitary-thyroid axis in lipopolysaccharide-induced acute illness in mice. *J Endocrinol* 182(2):315-323.
 28. Boelen A, Platvoet-ter Schiphorst MC, Bakker O, & Wiersinga WM (1995) The role of cytokines in the lipopolysaccharide-induced sick euthyroid syndrome in mice. *J Endocrinol* 146(3):475-483.
 29. Chow CC, Mak TW, Chan CH, & Cockram CS (1995) Euthyroid sick syndrome in pulmonary tuberculosis before and after treatment. *Ann Clin Biochem* 32 (Pt 4):385-391.
 30. Kawakami M, Usami I, Kuroki H, & Goto M (1993) [Thyroid hormones in patients with clinical stable pneumoconiosis]. *Nihon Kyobu Shikkan Gakkai Zasshi* 31(10):1215-1219.
 31. Okutan O, Kartaloglu Z, Onde ME, Bozkanat E, & Kunter E (2004) Pulmonary function tests and thyroid hormone concentrations in patients with chronic obstructive pulmonary disease. *Med Princ Pract* 13(3):126-128.
 32. Scoscia E, *et al.* (2004) Low triiodothyronine (T3) state: a predictor of outcome in respiratory failure? Results of a clinical pilot study. *Eur J Endocrinol* 151(5):557-560.
 33. Wawrzynska L, Sakowicz A, & Filipecki S (1996) [Euthyroid sick syndrome in patients with respiratory failure]. *Pneumonol Alergol Pol* 64 Suppl 2:193-199.
 34. Hong SB, *et al.* (2008) Essential role of pre-B-cell colony enhancing factor in ventilator-induced lung injury. *Am J Respir Crit Care Med* 178(6):605-617.
 35. Meyer NJ, *et al.* (2009) GADD45a is a novel candidate gene in inflammatory lung injury via influences on Akt signaling. *FASEB J* 23(5):1325-1337.
 36. Koh Y, *et al.* (1999) Heat shock response decreases endotoxin-induced acute lung injury in rats. *Respirology* 4(4):325-330.
 37. Wheeler AP & Bernard GR (2007) Acute lung injury and the acute respiratory distress syndrome: a clinical review. *Lancet* 369(9572):1553-1564.
 38. Zhao J, Yan Y, Salnikow K, Kluz T, & Costa M (2004) Nickel-induced down-regulation of serpin by hypoxic signaling. *Toxicol Appl Pharmacol* 194(1):60-68.

39. Atkinson D & Hill DL (2003) Reconstruction after rotational motion. *Magn Reson Med* 49(1):183-187.
40. Chakrabarti S & Patel KD (2005) Matrix metalloproteinase-2 (MMP-2) and MMP-9 in pulmonary pathology. *Exp Lung Res* 31(6):599-621.
41. Pesce JT, *et al.* (2009) Retnla (relmalpha/fizz1) suppresses helminth-induced Th2-type immunity. *PLoS Pathog* 5(4):e1000393.
42. Liao XH, *et al.* (2011) Distinct roles of deiodinases on the phenotype of Mct8 defect: a comparison of eight different mouse genotypes. *Endocrinology* 152(3):1180-1191.
43. Schneider MJ, *et al.* (2001) Targeted disruption of the type 2 selenodeiodinase gene (DIO2) results in a phenotype of pituitary resistance to T4. *Mol Endocrinol* 15(12):2137-2148.
44. Jacobson JR, *et al.* (2005) Simvastatin attenuates vascular leak and inflammation in murine inflammatory lung injury. *Am J Physiol Lung Cell Mol Physiol* 288(6):L1026-1032.
45. Leeper-Woodford SK & Detmer K (1999) Acute hypoxia increases alveolar macrophage tumor necrosis factor activity and alters NF-kappaB expression. *Am J Physiol* 276(6 Pt 1):L909-916.
46. Lentsch AB, Czermak BJ, Bless NM, & Ward PA (1998) NF-kappaB activation during IgG immune complex-induced lung injury: requirements for TNF-alpha and IL-1beta but not complement. *Am J Pathol* 152(5):1327-1336.
47. Moine P, *et al.* (2000) NF-kappaB regulatory mechanisms in alveolar macrophages from patients with acute respiratory distress syndrome. *Shock* 13(2):85-91.
48. Wright JG & Christman JW (2003) The role of nuclear factor kappa B in the pathogenesis of pulmonary diseases: implications for therapy. *Am J Respir Med* 2(3):211-219.
49. Wurfel MM, *et al.* (2008) Toll-like receptor 1 polymorphisms affect innate immune responses and outcomes in sepsis. *Am J Respir Crit Care Med* 178(7):710-720.
50. Fekete C, *et al.* (2004) Lipopolysaccharide induces type 2 iodothyronine deiodinase in the mediobasal hypothalamus: implications for the nonthyroidal illness syndrome. *Endocrinology* 145(4):1649-1655.
51. Zeold A, *et al.* (2006) Characterization of the nuclear factor-kappa B responsiveness of the human dio2 gene. *Endocrinology* 147(9):4419-4429.

52. Ma S-F, *et al.* (2010) Diodinase 2 (Dio2) is a novel candidate gene which confers susceptibility and severity in acute lung injury and ventilation-induced lung injury in European Americans. *American Thoracic Society*.
53. Chidakel A, Mentuccia D, & Celi FS (2005) Peripheral metabolism of thyroid hormone and glucose homeostasis. *Thyroid* 15(8):899-903.
54. Mebis L, Langouche L, Visser TJ, & Van den Berghe G (2007) The type II iodothyronine deiodinase is up-regulated in skeletal muscle during prolonged critical illness. *J Clin Endocrinol Metab* 92(8):3330-3333.
55. Mebis L & van den Berghe G (2009) The hypothalamus-pituitary-thyroid axis in critical illness. *Neth J Med* 67(10):332-340.
56. Palmer KC, Mari F, & Malian MS (1986) Cadmium-induced acute lung injury: compromised repair response following thyroidectomy. *Environ Res* 41(2):568-584.
57. Dulchavsky SA & Bailey J (1992) Triiodothyronine treatment maintains surfactant synthesis during sepsis. *Surgery* 112(2):475-479.
58. Inan M, *et al.* (2003) Thyroid hormone supplementation in sepsis: an experimental study. *Surg Today* 33(1):24-29.
59. Schneider MJ, *et al.* (2006) Targeted disruption of the type 1 selenodeiodinase gene (Dio1) results in marked changes in thyroid hormone economy in mice. *Endocrinology* 147(1):580-589.
60. Peng X, *et al.* (2004) Protective effects of sphingosine 1-phosphate in murine endotoxin-induced inflammatory lung injury. *Am J Respir Crit Care Med* 169(11):1245-1251.
61. Pohlenz J, *et al.* (1999) Improved radioimmunoassay for measurement of mouse thyrotropin in serum: strain differences in thyrotropin concentration and thyrotroph sensitivity to thyroid hormone. *Thyroid* 9(12):1265-1271.
62. Alfonso M, Arufe MC, & Duran R (1998) Validation of an EIA kit for determination of total thyroid hormones in rat serum. Effects of different anaesthetics. *J Physiol Biochem* 54(1):15-21.
63. Dumitrescu AM, *et al.* (2005) Mutations in SECISBP2 result in abnormal thyroid hormone metabolism. *Nat Genet* 37(11):1247-1252.

Figure legends

Figure. 1.- Serum TH and TSH levels in WT mice after ventilator induced lung injury (VILI). Serum T₃, TSH, T₄ and rT₃ concentrations in WT mice exposed to VILI

(open bars) compared with SB animals (black bars). Note that TSH levels were undetectable after VILI and were assigned a value equal to the sensitivity of the assay (10mU/L, indicated by a dash line) for statistical analysis. Mean values \pm SEM are depicted. Differences between groups are indicated: *, $P < 0.05$ and **, $P < 0.01$. SB, spontaneously breathing. N=8 animals per group.

Figure. 2.- D1, D2 and D3 mRNA levels and D2 protein levels and enzymatic activity in the lungs of WT animals exposed to VILI. Lung D1, D2 and D3 (A) mRNA levels in WT mice after VILI (open bars) compared to SB animals (black bars). Mean values \pm SEM are depicted. Significant differences between groups are indicated: *, $P < 0.05$; **, $P < 0.01$. N= 8 animals per group. Number of cycles in the quantitative PCR reaction are indicated below the bars (Ct) to indicate relative abundance of each enzyme. B) Immunohistochemical staining of D2 (brown) is shown for a SB WT mouse where D2 protein was graded as 1+ in the epithelium and 1+ in pulmonary endothelium. Minimal inflammatory cells were observed. Sections from a WT mouse exposed to VILI demonstrate 3+ D2 in the epithelium, 3+ in pulmonary endothelium. More inflammatory cells were observed but no immunoreactivity in these cells (indicated by asterisk). Staining of D2 in a section from a D2KO mouse. The absence of D2 staining shows the specificity of the antibody. Negligible D2 staining of a WT mice after VILI by using the preimmune serum (n=2 animals per group). C) D2 enzymatic activity after VILI (open bars) compared to SB animals (black bars). Mean values \pm SEM are depicted. Significant differences between groups are indicated: *, $P < 0.05$. N= 8 animals per group.

Fig. 3.- D2KO mice have increased susceptibility to VILI. A) BAL protein content in D2KO mice compared with WT mice exposed to VILI. VILI evoked significant

elevations in BAL protein levels in WT (*, $p < 0.05$) and D2KO mice (**, $P < 0.01$). B) Hematoxylin and eosin staining of representative lung sections of a WT and a D2KO mouse SB and VILI-exposed. No pathological differences between SB WT and D2KO mice. Cell infiltration in the alveolar wall and hyaline membrane formation were increased in WT mice exposed to VILI (indicated by green and red arrows respectively). Histology of a representative D2KO mouse exposed to VILI that shows higher polymorphonuclear cells infiltration and hyaline membrane formation compared to their correspondent WT mice (3 animals per group). C) Fold change of cytokines and chemokines (IL-6, IL-1 β , Cxcl1, Tnf- α and Cxcl2) by qPCR in WT (N=6) (black bars) or D2KO (N=6) mice (open bars) exposed to VILI relative to the SB animals control. Differences between groups are indicated: *, $P < 0.05$ and **, $P < 0.01$. D) Fold change of Hsp1, Serpine 3G, Mmp9 and RetIng by qPCR in WT (N=8) (black bars) or D2KO mice (N=6) (open bars) exposed to VILI relative to the SB animals control. Differences between groups are indicated: *, $P < 0.05$ and **, $P < 0.01$

Figure. 4. Effect of LT3 treatment on cytokine and chemokine expression in lungs of D2KO mice after VILI. Mice were treated with 0.2 μ g/100 gm L-T3 for 5 days subjected to VILI or SB two hours after the last injection. Fold change of markers of inflammation and injury by qPCR in WT (N=6), D2KO (N=6) and T-3 treated D2KO (n=6) mice exposed to VILI relative to the SB animals control. In general, protective markers of inflammation (Serpine 3g, Hsp1) generally increased with T3 treatment (although MMP9 and Rslg did not), while proinflammatory markers (Cxcl1, TNF, IL1b and Cxcl2) were suppressed with L-T3 (although IL6 did not). Differences between groups are indicated: *, $P < 0.05$ and **, $P < 0.01$.

Figure. 5.- Serum TH and TSH concentrations and D1 and D3 mRNA expression in D2KO mice after VILI. A) Serum T₃, TSH, T₄ and rT₃ concentrations in ventilated WT and D2KO mice (open bars) compared with SB animals (black bars). Note that after VILI the TSH levels in WT mice were undetectable and were assigned a value equal to the sensitivity of the assay (10mU/L, indicated by a dash line) for statistical analysis. Mean values \pm SEM are depicted. VILI vs SB *, P< 0.05 and **, P< 0.01 vs SB. N=6 animals per group. Lung D1 and D3 (B) mRNA levels in WT and D2KO mice after VILI compared with SB animals control. N= 8 animals per group. Mean values \pm SEM are depicted. Significant differences between groups are indicated: *, P< 0.05 and #, P< 0.05 vs WT SB.

Figure. 6.- Response to VILI on D1KO mice are comparable to WT mice. A) BAL protein content in WT and D1KO mice exposed to VILI compared with SB animals. Differences between groups are indicated. *, p<0.05. B) Hematoxylin and eosin staining of a lung section of a WT mouse and a D1KO mouse SB and after exposure to VILI. Histology of a VILI-exposed WT and D1KO mice shows higher polymorphonuclear cells infiltration and hyaline membrane formation with no differences between the two groups (3 animals per group). C) Fold changes of VILI biomarker genes (IL-6, IL-1 β , Cxcl1, Tnf- α and Cxcl2) by qPCR in WT and D1KO mice exposed to VILI relative to the SB animals control. *, P< 0.05 vs WT mice. Fold change of Hsp1, Serpine 3G, Mmp9 and Retlng (5D) by qPCR in WT (N=8) and D1KO mice (N=6) (open bars) exposed to VILI relative to the SB animals control.

Figure. 7.- Hypothyroid WT mice have increased susceptibility to VILI. BAL protein content in hypothyroid mice compared with euthyroid animals exposed to VILI. VILI evoked significant elevations in BAL protein levels in euthyroid mice (*,

p<0.05) and hypothyroid mice (*, P<0.05; ##, P< 0.01 vs SB euthyroid mice). mRNA levels of VILI biomarker genes, IL-6, IL-1 β , Cxcl1, Tnf- α and Cxcl by qPCR in euthyroid (N=8) and hypothyroid (N=6) SB and after VILI. Lung D2 mRNA and enzymatic activity in euthyroid and hypothyroid mice after VILI compared with SB animals control. N= 6 animals per group. Mean values \pm SEM are depicted *, P< 0.05 vs SB; **, P< 0.01 vs SB; ***, P< 0.001 vs SB; #, P< 0.05 vs euthyroid VILI; ##, P< 0.01 vs euthyroid VILI; ###, P< 0.001 vs euthyroid VILI.

Figure. 8.- Model of lung D2 induction by VILI. VILI is characterized by increases in inflammatory cytokine expression and activation of mediators of immune and inflammatory responses such as NF-kB. The pro-inflammatory cytokines increase hypothalamic D2 (17) and cause central hypothyroidism that might be responsible for the low serum T₃. The induction of D2 in the lung by mechanical ventilation might be adaptative to the low T₃ circulating levels or due to the local activation of NF-kB.

Figure1

Figure 3

Figure 4; Proinflammatory markers in WT vs D2 KO mice

Figure 5

Figure 6

Figure 7

Figure 8

